

Synthesis of Certain Acridine Derivatives Structurally Related to Some Chemotherapeutic Agents

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Reaction of acridone with thionylchloride gave 9-chloroacridine which on reaction with thiourea gave 9-mercaptoacridine (2). A new series of 9-(N-aryl/heterocyclic carboxamidomethyl thio)acridines (4 and 5) have been synthesised via the reaction of 2 with N-aryl/heterocyclic-2-chloroacetamides. Also, 9-(mercaptoacetyl N-aryluroido)-acridine derivatives (6) have been prepared.

INSECTICIDAL, bactericidal, antimalarial and local anaesthetic properties are exhibited by acridine derivatives¹⁻⁵. Acetamides, in which amido-H has been substituted by aromatic or heterocyclic moieties, are known to exhibit local anaesthetic activity⁶. Also, N-chloroacetyl ureas have shown fungicidal and antibacterial activity⁷⁻¹⁰. It was, therefore, considered of interest to synthesise a series of 9-(N-aryl/heterocyclic carboxamidomethyl thio)acridines (4 and 5) and 9-[mercaptoacetyl(substituted aryl) urea]acridines (6) in the hope that compounds with biological activity might evolve.

9-Chloroacridine (1) was prepared by ring closure of diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid using phosphorous oxychloride¹¹. 9-Chloroacridine hydrochloride was obtained in high yield via a novel route by reacting acridone with thionyl chloride in presence of a few drops of dimethylformamide.

Reaction of acridone with phosphorous pentasulphide in dry pyridine gave 9-mercaptoacridine (2). Another alternative for preparing 2 is the reaction of 1 with thiourea in ethanol. It is known that 2 reacted with alkyl halides¹² to give the corresponding S-alkyl derivatives. Treatment of 2 with ethyl chloroacetate in acetone in presence of potassium carbonate furnished 9-(ethoxycarbonylmethyl thio)acridine (3a). The latter was condensed with aniline in ethanol to get 9-(phenyl)aminoacridine, instead of the expected amide derivative. The structure of 9-(phenyl)aminoacridine was ascertained authentically via the direct interaction of 1 with aniline according to Bank's method¹³.

Reaction of 1 with mercaptoacetic acid or of 2 with chloroacetic acid gave 9-(carboxymethyl thio)acridine (3b), which was reacted with aniline, p-toluidine and 2-aminothiazole in dimethylformamide in presence of EEDQ as condensing agent¹⁴, to give the corresponding amides 4a, 4g and 5a, respectively in low yield.

Accordingly, the new 9-(N-aryl/heterocyclic carboxamidomethyl thio)acridines (4) and (5) were

prepared via the reaction of 2 and N-aryl/heterocyclic-2-chloroacetamides in acetone in presence of potassium carbonate, in good yield.

Also, reaction of 1 with N-chloroacetyl substituted aryl urea afforded 9-[mercaptoacetyl (substituted aryl) urea]acridines (6).

3a : C₂H₅
b : H

5a : H
b : -C₆H₄-Br-*p*
c : -C₆H₄-CH₃-*p*
d : -C₆H₄-OCH₃-*p*

4a : -C₆H₅
b : -C₆H₄-Br-*p*
c : -C₆H₄-Cl-*o*
d : C₆H₄-Cl-*p*
e : C₆H₄-COOH-*o*
f : C₆H₄-COOH-*p*
g : C₆H₄-CH₃-*p*
h : C₆H₄-OCH₃-*p*
i : C₆H₄-NO₂-*p*
j : C₆H₄-COCH₃-*p*
k : CH₂-C₆H₅
l : C₁₀H₇- α
m : C₁₀H₇- β

6a : -C₆H₅
b : -C₆H₄-OH-*o*
c : -C₆H₄-CH₃-*m*
d : -C₆H₄-CH₃-*p*
e : -CH₂-C₆H₅

7a

7b : O
7c : S

On the other hand, reaction of 1 with 2, 2-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole and 2-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole yielded 9,9'-diacridyl sulphide (7a), 2-(9-acridyl thio)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (7b) and 2-(9-acridyl thio)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (7c), respectively.

Structures of the compounds 3-7 were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, ir and uv spectra. The ir spectrum of 3a showed absorption band at 1730 cm^{-1} ($-\text{COOEt}$), while that of 4 and 5 showed absorption bands at $3260\text{--}3280$ (NH) and $1660\text{--}1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (CO). The ir spectra of 6 showed absorption bands in the regions $3290\text{--}3300$, $1710\text{--}1700$ and $1690\text{--}1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $-\text{NH}$ and CO groups, respectively.

The uv spectra of 1, 3a, 4a,b,d,f, 5a,b,c were characterized by principal absorption band at $250\text{--}258\text{ m}\mu$.

Experimental

The purity of the prepared compounds was checked by tlc, using benzene-ethylacetate mixture. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 200 G spectrophotometer. UV spectra were taken in ethanol on a Pye-Unicam SP 8000 spectrophotometer. Melting points are uncorrected.

9-Chloroacridine (1): A mixture of acridone (10 g; 0.05 mole) and thionyl chloride (0.3 mole) in dry benzene was refluxed for 3 hr in presence of a few drops of dimethylformamide. The yellow crystalline product was collected and washed several times with benzene. Crystallisation from benzene-methanol mixture gave 9-chloroacridine hydrochloride, yield 94%, m.p. 179° . (Found: C, 61.46; H, 3.82; N, 5.66; Cl, 28.69. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_9\text{NCl}_2$ requires C, 61.20; H, 3.60; N, 5.60; Cl, 28.40%).

Treatment of the product with dilute ammonium hydroxide gave 9-chloroacridine as a pale gray crystalline product, m.p. 120° (Lit.¹⁵ 120°).

9-Mercaptoacridine (2): Equimolecular proportions of acridone and phosphorous pentasulphide in dry pyridine were refluxed for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into water, the reddish crystalline product was filtered, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid followed by water. Crystallisation from ethanol gave 9-mercaptoacridine, yield 81%, m.p. $247^\circ\text{--}49^\circ$ (Lit.¹⁶ 247°). Treatment of 1 in boiling ethanol with thiourea gave 2 as reddish-yellow crystalline product, yield 85%.

9-(Ethoxycarbonylmethyl thio)acridine (3a): To a solution of 2 (0.01 mole) in acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate was added ethyl chloroacetate (0.012 mole) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the solvent was evaporated. Crystallisation of the residue gave 3a, yield 60%.

Treatment of 3a (0.5 g) with hydrazine hydrate (2 ml; 90%) in boiling ethanol for 2 hr gave 9-(phenyl)aminoacridine as yellow crystals, m.p.

$220\text{--}21^\circ$. The same product was obtained from 1 and aniline.

Reaction of 3b with aniline, p-toluidine and 2-aminothiazole (4a, g and 5a): N-Ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxy-1,2,-dihydroquinoline¹⁴ (0.0025 mole) was added portionwise to a mixture of 3b and the corresponding amine (0.002 mole) in dimethylformamide (10 ml) at room temperature during 10 min. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the crude product was crystallised from ethanol, yield 40-50% (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3-7

Compd. No.	m.p. $^\circ\text{C}$	Analysis %					
		Calcd	Found	C	H	N	S
3a	84	68.69	5.05	4.71	10.77		
		68.12	5.21	4.51	11.10		
3b	210-12	66.91	4.08	5.20	11.90		
		66.81	4.36	5.40	12.36		
4a	184	73.26	4.65	8.14	9.30		
		73.71	4.31	8.31	9.70		
4b	215	59.57	3.55	6.62	7.57		
		59.41	3.21	6.41	7.36		
4c	180	66.66	3.97	7.41	8.47		
		66.51	3.57	7.31	7.96		
4d	186	66.66	3.97	7.41	8.47		
		66.41	3.51	7.31	8.31		
4e	208	86.01	4.12	7.22	8.25		
		86.31	4.52	7.61	8.51		
4f	212	86.04	4.12	7.22	8.25		
		86.31	4.41	7.41	8.65		
4g	200	73.74	5.30	7.82	8.94		
		73.61	5.39	7.71	8.53		
4h	208	70.58	4.31	7.49	8.56		
		70.41	4.61	7.61	8.11		
4i	226	64.78	3.86	10.80	8.33		
		64.38	3.39	10.41	8.70		
4j	192	71.50	4.66	7.25	8.29		
		71.31	4.31	7.60	8.71		
4k	190	73.74	5.02	7.82	8.94		
		73.28	5.42	7.46	8.64		
4l	202	76.14	4.57	7.11	8.12		
		76.61	4.34	7.46	8.56		
4m	221	76.14	7.57	7.11	8.12		
		76.61	7.16	7.61	8.31		
5a	210	61.53	3.70	11.97	13.23		
		61.71	3.46	11.36	13.16		
5b	205	56.93	3.16	8.30	12.65		
		56.56	3.41	8.71	12.71		
5c	232	68.02	4.31	9.52	14.51		
		68.36	4.76	9.81	14.10		
5d	208	65.65	4.16	9.19	14.00		
		65.76	4.66	9.59	14.41		
6a	189-90	68.39	4.15	10.88	8.29		
		68.71	4.60	10.48	8.71		
6b	173-74	68.98	4.71	10.42	7.94		
		68.46	4.60	10.31	8.50		
6c	184	68.98	4.71	10.42	7.94		
		68.67	4.61	10.31	7.36		
6d	192	68.98	4.71	10.42	7.94		
		68.71	4.62	10.56	8.31		
6e	190	68.98	4.71	10.42	7.94		
		68.60	4.51	10.91	7.46		
7a	265-67	80.41	4.12	7.22	8.35		
		79.81	4.31	7.38	7.67		
7b	182-83	70.98	3.66	11.33	9.01		
		70.32	3.41	11.61	8.46		
7c	223-24	67.92	3.50	11.32	17.22		
		67.66	3.22	11.16	16.64		

Preparation of 4, 5 and 6 : Treatment of 2 with N-aryl/heterocyclic-2-chloroacetamides or N-chloroacetyl substituted aryl urea in acetone and potassium carbonate as previously described, gave 4, 5 and 6, respectively, yield 80-85% (Table 1).

Preparation of 7a-c : Treatment of 1 with 2, 2-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole or 2-mercapto-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole under the same conditions gave 7a-c respectively, yield 83-85% (Table 1).

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